

CONSULTING SERVICES: RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF THE PARTIES

Asadov Shahriddin Fahriddin ugli

Tashkent State Law University,

Lecturer of the Department of Private Law

e-mail: shahriddinasadov@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7559890>

ANNOTATION

This article discusses consulting services and their features, the essence of their content and the participants in these relationships. A brief history of the existence of advisory and consulting services, the necessity of their existence and the types of consulting services that are currently available are considered. A brief analysis of the features and individual aspects of these services was carried out, with an idea of the types of consulting services currently provided. The issues of the legal status of the participants in these relations and their rights and obligations in the relationship, including the duties and obligations of the service provider, the procedure for providing these services to him and the rules that must be observed in this process, were also discussed. The user of the services also touched upon the actions necessary to achieve the results obtained from these services, and expressed his opinion on the need for a clear definition of the rights and obligations of the parties for the effective regulation of these relations.

Keywords: consulting services, the parties providing consulting services, the user of consulting services, the provider of consulting services, types of consulting services, legal advice, consulting services in the field of accounting and finance, civil liability of the parties to the contract.

The rights and obligations between the parties arise in accordance with the agreement between them, this is the most important feature of civil legal relations. In civil law, it is established that this agreement must be voluntary, that neither party can force the other party to reach an agreement (conclusion of a contract) to extend the validity of certain actions or refrain from certain actions, that an agreement based on coercion will have legal consequences established by law[1]. It is also indicated that it is possible to forcibly conclude a contract only in a certain case.

So, according to the general rule, we realized that the conclusion of the contract can be made at the discretion of the parties, at the conclusion of the contract, each party can conclude a contract on favorable terms for it, in its own interests. The provision of consulting or consulting services in a certain area also increases in accordance with the desire of the parties to use these services and provide these services. At this point, it should be noted that the provision of consulting and consulting services has a number of specific features [1]. For example, users of the service are required to express their consent to use the service and pay for it in accordance with the established procedure, as well as consent to the use of information related to them during the provision of the service.

Various social relations arising in society require knowledge of the features of social relations that a person enters into it. Also, a person may feel the need for more detailed information about this situation in various situations that he will face. The desire to find answers to various questions that arise in the process of increasing entrepreneurial activity in practice, or to questions that arise in connection with the question of what interests a person, necessitated the emergence of subjects who can provide qualified explanations on the actions

performed [2]. This need is reflected in the modern world in various consulting services in a number of spheres of public life.

These services can be organized in various spheres of society, depending on the existing need. Due to the nature of the service provided, these services may have different characteristics. This may be the provision of explanations on a specific situation or circumstances, the provision of specific information or the provision of various information support for any process.

Currently, the provision of consulting or consulting services in a certain area has turned into a full-fledged professional activity. The development of consulting relations also creates the need to regulate public relations in this area. In order to effectively regulate these relations, it is desirable to analyze the content of these relations.

Consulting services are provided on the basis of an agreement between the service provider and the user. This agreement can be concluded in the form of a contract (agreement). In general, in the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on contracts for the provision of paid services, this contract can also be used in the process of providing consulting and consulting services [3]. In general, it was noted above that consulting services should be carried out on the basis of an agreement between the parties to the service.

Currently, various consulting services are provided in various spheres of public life. Each person and each individual enterprise needs reliable information, appropriate explanations and support in a particular area to achieve the desired results and develop their own activities in various situations. The development of its activities and the provision of solutions to existing problems, in turn, reveals the need to have relevant knowledge and skills or use the services of persons with the necessary knowledge and skills. Due to the current need, consulting services are now penetrating into various areas and sectors of public life. In addition, the issues that can be solved with the help of consulting are also very diverse. Sometimes it can also consist of a whole set of tasks, and sometimes only of services that are provided in a narrow area. For example, accounting consulting can be recognized as a type of use of consulting services provided by involving a specialized company or an individual to solve problems related to accounting. Therefore, when it comes to the concept of consulting, the similarity of this concept with the generally accepted, absolute single definition is given. Consulting services is defined as a process that consists in solving existing organizational or managerial tasks with the help of external specialists. Professional consultants from a certain field are invited to work in the company. Experts assess the situation, find out the cause of the problems and put forward their suggestions and recommendations to eliminate the existing problem. Consulting services go hand in hand to solve various problems of socio-economic life. For example, if we look at consulting services in the field of entrepreneurship and business, then these services are provided not only when an entity faces some problems and difficulties in the course of its activities, but also when an enterprise has the opportunity to expand its activities and increase its capabilities, for this it is necessary to study the market. This service can be especially useful for newly created business entities, since newly created and inexperienced entities will not always have the opportunity to fully study the requirements of the market, this can be avoided due to their financial and organizational capabilities. In this case, the most effective way for this enterprise is to use the services of external specialists [4]. Also, the Company may seek to enter new markets, which, in turn, will require additional labor. In such situations, it is advisable to use consulting services. This is due to the fact that it not only reduces the amount of costs incurred, but also saves the time needed to achieve the desired result, and allows it to be achieved faster than the intended result.

Counseling services are currently provided in a number of areas, including the following: Psychological counseling in the field of providing psychological counseling; Financial, accounting consulting services in the field of audit; Medical consulting services (this service

has other aspects than the provision of medical services, so medical consulting services may consist of various tips and recommendations based on the results of medical analysis); Consulting services on information technologies in the field of Internet technologies; Marketing consulting services in the field of marketing application; Consulting and other legal services.

These services have their own characteristics, depending on the nature of the work performed. Although some of these services have been in existence for quite some time and the relationships within this service are carefully regulated, some of them are relatively new types of services, and the relationships themselves, which are the basis for the provision of these services, are relatively new relationships. For example, the mechanism of consulting services in the field of psychological counseling is quite sufficient [5]. The analysis of problems related to a person and his psychological state, and through it the solution of various psychological problems existing in a person's life, has been evaluated for many years as an effective mechanism for effectively eliminating existing problems in a person's life. Within the framework of these relations, the service provider analyzes a particular problem existing in the relationship of the service user and suggests the causes of its occurrence and measures to eliminate it.

The obligations of the entities providing consulting and services can be continued not only after the completion of the actions specified in the subject of the contract, but also after the completion of the actions specified in the contract. This obligation should consist in the fact that the service provider does not disclose any information that became known to him about the user of the services during the provision of the service [6]. You can imagine this aspect as a different aspect of these services from others provided on a reimbursable basis. That is, the rights and obligations of the parties in other services provided for a fee will end with the provision of these services. In the case of consulting and consulting services, the service provider will have a number of obligations, even after the completion of the service provided by the contract. It turns out that during the provision of these services, the service provider receives from the user the information necessary for the provision of the service about him. This data may contain information about the personal life of the service user, his medical and physical parameters or his psychological state, as well as the commercial or business secrets of the service user.

Disclosure or other misuse of this information entails appropriate legal consequences. If their information is disclosed by the service provider in a way contrary to his will, unlawfully, or such information is used without his consent, the service user may demand compensation for the damage caused to him, as well as compensation for the moral damage caused.

References:

1. Greiner L.E., Metzger R.O. Consulting to management. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, Prentice Hall, 1983. P.
2. Асадов, Ш. Ф. У. (2022). КОНСУЛЬТАЦИОННЫЕ УСЛУГИ: КАК УСЛУГИ ОКАЗЫВАЕМЫЕ НА ВОЗМЕЗДНОМ ОСНОВЕ. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(7), 716-723.
3. Beckhard R., Harris R.T. Organisational transitions: Managing complex change. MA, Addison-Wesley, 1977.
4. Asadov, S. F. O. G. L. (2021). FUQAROLIK-HUQUQIY MUNOSABATLARDA DAVLAT ISHTIROKI (DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK MISOLIDA). Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(11), 789-799.
5. Раҳмонқулов Ҳ. Фуқаролик ҳуқуқининг субъектлари, ўқув қўлланма – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2008. 170 бет

6. Atalikova, G. S., & Asadov, S. F. O. G. L. (2022). MASLAHAT VA KONSALTING XIZMATLARI: HUQUQIY TARTIBGA SOLISH MASALALARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 299-309.
7. Management Consultants 1996 World Conference "The Roles and Activities of the Consulting Business toward the 21st Century". Yokohama: Zen-Noh-Ren, 1996. P. 165-167.
8. Ibrohimov, A. A. O., Koryogdiyev, B. U. O., & Tojiboyev, S. Z. (2022). KORPORATIV NIQOBLARNI OLIB TASHLASH KONSEPSIYASI VA UNI O'ZBEKISTON KORPORATIV HUQUQIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 1068-1082.
9. Koryogdiyev, B. U. O. (2021). BITIMNI HAQIQIY EMAS DEB TOPISH VA UNING OQIBATLARINI QOLLASH FUQAROLIK HUQUQLARINI HIMOYA QILISH VOSITASI SIFATIDA. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 211-225.
10. Imomniyozov, D. B. O. G. L. (2021). IKKIYOQLAMA SOLIQQA TORTMASLIK PRINSIPINING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 1174-1182.
11. Abdikhakimov, I. (2023, January). Trademark and copyright infringements in social media. In *Science-Zone Online Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 187-200).
12. Toshmuxammadov, A., & To'xtayev, O. K. (2022). JAMOAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING IJTIMOIIY VA HUQUQIY ZARURIYATI. *Elita. uz-Elektron Ilmiy Jurnal*, 1(1), 5-16.
13. Абидина М. Три стороны этики в консалтинге. // Управление персоналом. 2006. - № 8. - С. 19-26.

